

20 Questions about Service Design

Service Design is the process that creates, maintains and improves the value of a service for both service users and providers. It is iteratively performed throughout the entire lifecycle of a service and helps to organise all processes, technologies and interactions that are essential for its delivery. Our 20 questions guide you through all relevant dimensions.

1. Do you understand all **requirements** issued towards your service? Do you have a common understanding with your stakeholders? Can the requirements guide the creation of a valid service? Have all conflicts between them been resolved?
2. Which **components** are needed to deliver the required functionality?
3. What are potential **interactions**?
 - a. How do the **service components** interact with each other?
 - b. How do your **users** interact with your service?
 - c. How do **other services** interact with your service?
4. How can you establish the service's **integration into the RDM landscape** (on a regional, national (including Base4NFDI!) and European level)?
 - a. How does the service make **contributions to a FAIR data landscape**?
5. Which **technologies** can deliver the needed functionality?
6. Are you using components with **open licenses**?
 - a. Are all licenses **compatible** with licenses of your own components?
 - b. Are there **any justifications** to not use components with **open licenses**?
7. Which **standards** does your service need to comply with?
8. How do you facilitate **data management and delivery** (including provenance)?
9. How do you ensure **(data) persistence**?
10. How do you ensure high **service quality**?
 - a. What is the **definition of quality attributes** for your service?
11. What is your concept for handling **personal user data**?
12. How do you **secure** your service? Which **security measures** do you apply?
 - a. How do you protect its **integrity**?
 - b. Which are the **critical assets**?
13. How will you **manage security incidents** and **integrity violations**?
14. What is the required **availability** of your service?
 - a. How do you **avoid downtimes and non-responsive behaviour**?
 - b. Where do you need **testing** and **system monitoring**?
15. With what do you need to be **compatible**? How do you ensure **interoperability**?

16. Do you have a strategy for **scaling up** the service if demand increases?
17. How do you initiate and increase **stakeholder engagement** with the service (including end-users, new developers, community managers, trainers, students, politicians, funders, ...)?
 - a. How do you create a great **user experience** and maximise **inclusivity**?
18. How do you document and share information about the service? What is your strategy for **knowledge management**?
19. How do you manage **customer relations**? How will you reach your users? How will they reach you?
 - a. How do you **announce changes** to the service?
20. Have you assigned all **responsibilities** and identified all roles required for the operation of the service?

Have you started writing your answers down by now?*

Good documentation helps you to...

- ... keep the design aligned with requirements and policies,
- ... keep track of dependencies,
- ... defend design decisions ten years from now,
- ... efficiently develop the service and update its design.

* A documentation of your service design is also a requirement for completing the Base4NFDI Initialisation Phase (Deliverable D.Ini.3). Cf. Wittenhorst, T., Ganske, A., Lehmenkühler, D., & Arndt, S. (2026). Base4NFDI – Requirements for Completion of Initialisation Phase. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19662240>.

!/? Need guidance?

Write to: [base4nfdi-ta1\[at\]lists.nfdi.de](mailto:base4nfdi-ta1[at]lists.nfdi.de)

Use our Service Design Guide: Arndt, S., Ganske, A., & Lehmenkühler, D. (2026). Service Design Guide (Version 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19675991>.

Funded by DFG as part of NFDI.

Grant Numbers: 521453681, 521460392, 521462155, 521463400, 521466146, 521471126, 521473512, 521474032, 521475185, 521476232